

Estimation of Clotrimazole residue in swab samples via validated UPLC method

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Abstract : An ultra performance liquid chromatographic (UPLC) method was developed for simultaneous determination of antifungal ointment and active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) residues. A new, generic method is presented, with which it is possible to verify the cleaning process of antifungal drug producing equipment line used for the production of various pharmaceuticals. The UPLC method was validated using an UPLC (BEH C18) column with a particle size of 1.7 μ (50 mm \times 2.1 mm) and methanol-buffer (80 : 20, v/v) as mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min. Method development and method validation for cleaning control analysis are described. The rapid UPLC method is suitable for cleaning control assays within good manufacturing practices (GMP) of the pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords : UPLC, standard, cleaning validation, recovery, precision, stability.

Introduction

In pharmaceutical industry the cleaning procedure is one of the most important tasks to avoid the cross contamination for subsequent batches manufactured in the same equipment. Analytical methods used to determine residuals or contaminants should be specific for the substance or the class of substances to be assayed (e.g. API residue, detergent residue) and be validated prior to cleaning validation¹⁻³. Guidelines recommend thin layer chromatography (TLC), UV photometric, total organic carbon analysis (TOC), conductivity, gas chromatography (GC) and conventional high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) methods for cleaning control or validation⁴. The use of other analytical methods, including capillary gas chromatography⁵, over-pressured layer chromatography (OPLC)⁶ or micellar electro kinetic chromatography (MEKC)⁷, have also been described. Ion mobility spectrometry (IMS)⁸ and TOC⁹ have the advantage of speed over the above mentioned methods but TOC is not specific and IMS is usually not available at pharmaceutical manufacturing facilities. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)^{10,11} and ultra performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS)¹² techniques applied in pharmaceutical cleaning verification have the advantage of improved sensitivity, selectivity and general applicability even for UV-inactive compounds. However, these techniques are more expensive

than the other techniques mentioned above and not widespread yet in cleaning control analysis. Nowadays HPLC-UV is the most commonly applied technique for cleaning control and validation¹³⁻¹⁸. In liquid chromatography, the analysis time can be reduced by using small columns packed with 2 μ m particles. In addition, with 2 μ m particles, due to the higher efficiency and smaller retention volume, sensitivity is also improved, compared to conventional HPLC. However, extra column effects are more significant for scaled down separations, therefore it is essential to minimize extra column dispersion. A dedicated low dispersion system for ultra-high pressure separation (UPLC) with the particle size of stationary phases reduced down to 1.7 μ m small dwell and extra column volume is able to work up to 1000 bar (15000 psi). In such a way the analysis time could be reduced down to 1-3 min, without the loss of resolution and sensitivity^{19,20}. It seems that in the future UPLC systems with elevated pressure and/or temperature will replace the conventional HPLC gradually in all areas of liquid chromatography including pharmaceutical analysis^{21,22}. The aim of this study was to demonstrate the applicability of UPLC to these purposes by developing, validating and applying an UPLC/UV method to determine the residues of UV-active Clotrimazole molecule as a antifungal category, in support of cleaning control and validation for formulation ointment plant. However, no paper can be found in

the literature in which the UPLC determination of molecule are described and applied for cleaning control analysis.

Clotrimazole USP :

Chemical name : 1-[(2-Chlorophenyl)diphenylmethyl]-1*H*-imidazole.

Physical state and appearance : Solid (Solid crystalline powder).

Melting point : 148 °C (298.4 °F).

Solubility :

Soluble in acetone. Very slightly soluble or practically insoluble in water.

Category : Antifungal.

Fig. 1. Structure of Clotrimazole.

Experimental

Reagent and solvents :

Methanol HPLC grade and dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate (AR grade) were purchased from Merck (Germany). Water was purified using a Milli-Q® equipment (Millipore). The reference materials are used as RS USP (United State Pharmacopeia). Their purity used 99.40% for reference standard, Waters UPLC® BEH C18 column with a particle size of 1.7u (50 mm × 2.1 mm) was purchased from Waters Ltd., Ireland. Swabs for sampling were purchased from Hi media (Mumbai, India).

Equipment :

Throughout the measurements and quantifications, Waters Acquity UPLC® H class with TUV system with Empower software from Waters Ltd., Milford, MA 01757, USA was employed.

Chromatographic conditions :

The mobile phases were prepared by mixing appropriate amount of HPLC grade methanol and buffer (4.5 g KH₂PO₄ in 1000 ml of Milli-Q water). The mixtures were degassed by sonication for 5 min. The stock solutions of

reference standards (Clotrimazole USP) were dissolved in methanol (10 µg). The solution for method development was diluted from the stock solutions with 40% water + 60% methanol solvent mix. The concentration of the test analyses was equivalent with the calculated maximum allowable residue limit in the reference solution. Isocratic mode of chromatography was used and mobile phase optimization, swabbed and rinsed blank solutions were also injected. Diluent (40% water + 60% methanol) solutions injected as a blank along with swab blank rinse with same solvent. A Waters UPLC® BEH C18 column with a particle size of 1.7u (50 mm × 2.1 mm) was used for basic runs and optimization. Isocratic method are selected at a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min were used. Detection at 215 nm was applied. Isocratic program, column temperature, injection volume and flow rate were optimized.

Standard and sample preparation :

Standard :

Weighed accurately about 25 mg Clotrimazole USP standard and transfer into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Added about 70 ml of diluents and sonicated to dissolve. Cooled to room temperature. Diluted up to mark with diluents (250 ppm stock). Pipette out 4 ml of above solution into 100 ml volumetric flask. Diluted up to mark with diluents and mix (10 ppm).

Sample preparation :

Taken 0.4 ml of standard stock solution on 10 × 10 SS plate. Allowed it to dry in air. After drying swabbed the plate using a sterilized swab stick as per swabbing procedure given in the below following diagram. Put the swab stick in stoppered glass tube and add 5 ml of diluent and sonicated for 5 min and diluted to 10 ml with diluents.

Fig. 2. Swab sampling procedure.

Establishing cleaning limits :

The acceptable limit for the drug residue must ensure the absence of cross contamination for subsequent batches

manufactured in the affected equipment²³. FDA's guidance for determining residue limits requires a logical, practical, achievable and verifiable determination practice². Until a technology and the equipment line are not finalized, the cleaning process cannot be validated, but just verified. It has to be taken into consideration that the product list and technologies may get modified.

This concept allows the establishment of limits not depending on the order of production. Preset limits for the analytical procedure can be applied. The basic principle of cleaning verification/validation is that the patient should not take more than 0.1 % of the standard therapeutic dose (effective dose). The calculation formula is based on the dosage criteria^{24,25}.

$$MAC = \frac{STD}{SF} \cdot \frac{(SBS)}{(LWSD)_{min}}$$

MAC is the maximum allowable carryover, STD is the minimal daily dose (active weight) of previous product, and SF is a safety factor (1000), SBS is the smallest batch size of the subsequent product and LWSD is the maximum daily dose (product weight) of the following product. An additional criterion is the 10 ppm (part per million) limit²⁵. According to the 10 ppm criterion not more than 10 ppm of the previously manufactured product is allowed to appear in the subsequent product. If the value, which is obtained from the calculation based on the dosage criterion, is greater than 10 ppm, then the 10 ppm

criterion is applied. The acceptance limit for residues (LA) is expressed in g/dm².

$$LA = \frac{MAC \cdot A \cdot R}{TA}$$

LA is the acceptance limit, A is the sampling area, and R is the recovery of the sampling method and TA is the total production line area.

Method validation parameters :

Specificity :

This experiment is carried out to demonstrate the specificity of method by identification of Clotrimazole and interference of blank and blank swab with the main peak. After injecting the solution of blank, blank swab, Clotrimazole standard solution and swabbed test solution, it has been observed that there is no interference at the retention time of Clotrimazole in blank and blank swab solution. Hence this method is considered specific for the Clotrimazole residue determinations.

Linearity of response :

Linearity of response was assessed by injecting standards prepared in sample solvent. The concentration range of compounds was investigated from the quantization limit (QL) up to the 150% of the maximum theoretical value (range : 0.25 ppm to 15 ppm) – The results were analyzed by linear regression. The correlation coefficients, r^2 , were found $r^2 > 0.99$.

Fig. 3. For specificity overview.

Fig. 4. Linearity chart (0.25 ppm to 15 ppm).

Accuracy :

Samples for recovery test were prepared as follows : reference materials in the range of LOQ–150% of limit concentration ($n = 6$) were spiked to 10 cm × 10 cm model surfaces. The surfaces selected for the recovery study are SS plate and glass plate. Clotrimazole reference standard were pipette from stock solutions (dissolved in methanol : water 60 : 40) and spread evenly on the model surfaces and allowed to dry. Sterile swabs were taken and swabbing was done from left to right and top to bottom and was diluted to get the desired concentrations. The concentrations prepared were LOQ level, 50% level, 100% level and 150% level. Wipes the swabs were placed in test tubes and 10 ml of freshly prepared sample solvent (methanol-water 60 : 40, v/v) was added and then sonicated for 5 min to produce the complete dissolution of compounds from the swab. In all cases sample concentrations were determined by reference to a calibration line (3 points) constructed from standards containing the respective analyte in LOQ–150% around the analytical limit concentration.

After preparation of all the concentrations, they were injected against 10 ppm reference standard solution. The results calculated and the recovery found more than 90% at each concentration level.

Precision :

Precision of the method has been demonstrated in following ways :

System precision :

The system precision has been demonstrated by injecting the Clotrimazole reference standard solution prepared in diluent (methanol : water 60 : 40) in six replicated and measured the RSD. The RSD observed less than 2.0%.

Method precision :

Method precision carried out by evaluating test preparation six times against standard solution and RSD of results has been calculated and found less than 2.0%.

Intermediate precision :

Intermediate precision has been established by injecting the test solution by different analyst on different day. RSD of result calculated of both method precision and intermediate precision. RSD found below 2.0%.

Limit of quantitation and detection :

Quantitation limits (LOQ) and detection limits (LOD) were determined by the regression method. Diluted concentrations of Clotrimazole standard solution has been prepared in range 0.25 ppm to 15 ppm. The solutions

Fig. 5. Recovery% evaluated on SS/glass surfaces.

were injected and slope and standard deviations of regression has been calculated^{26,27}.

Then LOQ and LOD calculated using following formulas :

$$\text{Predicted LOQ} = \frac{10 \times \text{STDEV}}{\text{Slope}}$$

$$\text{Predicted LOD} = \frac{3.3 \times \text{STDEV}}{\text{Slope}}$$

In the laboratory RSD < 10% for LOQ concentration and RSD < 33% for LOD concentration criteria are used for the methods of cleaning verification. Another term for LOD - in the laboratory - is that it must be lower than the 50% of analytical limit. The sensitivity of the method is proved to be sufficient for each compound.

Stability of analytical solution :

The stability of sample solution was studied on standard solutions at the concentration of cleaning limits (10 ppm) the solutions were stored in a sample compartment and are chromatographed up to 48 h at intervals 2, 4, 8, 12, 24, 36 and 48 h time. RSD < 2% criterion is used for the methods of cleaning verification. Peak areas should spread uniformly and without tendency when plotted against the time for each compound. There were no detectable degradants on the chromatograms.

Robustness :

Robustness of method to be checked at following conditions :

- (i) Change in flow rate : 0.5 ml/min \pm 0.05 ml/min
 - (A) 0.55 ml/min
 - (B) 0.45 ml/min
- (ii) Change in wavelength : 215 nm \pm 2 nm
 - (A) 217 nm
 - (B) 213 nm
- (iii) Change in concentration of mobile phase
 - (A) Methanol : buffer (792 : 208)
 - (B) Methanol : buffer (808 : 192)

The effects of chromatographic parameters were predicted via the checking the system suitability, based on the data generated during the basic model runs of method development^{26,27}.

Results

Method validation :

The UPLC method was validated. Data are summarized in Table 1. For system precision and suitability; six repetitions of injection from standard solution were used. The acceptance criteria for system suitability were as follows : tailing factor of Clotrimazole peak should not be more than 2.0% and the RSD of peak areas generated by five injections is lower than 2.0% for Clotrimazole peak. Specificity, linearity over the range of interest, accuracy (recovery from different types of surfaces) in the range of LOQ-150% of analytical cleaning limit, precision and limit of quantitation and detection were determined. The mean accuracy (recovery) from glass plate and SS plate are acceptable for this type of analysis (recovery > 90%), they are corrected by a recovery factor during routine analysis. For the robustness test a standard experimental design was applied to estimate the effect of chromatographic parameters.

Recovery study :

The surface of equipment is mostly made of stainless steel but recovery study has also been established at glass plate. These glass parts are the most critical in correlation with cleaning and sampling in our experience. The recovery study has been carried out in the range of LOQ to 150% level. The recovery found to be more than 90% at each level.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to develop a fast method for the cleaning validation process of the lotion and ointment equipment line. A fast, isocratic UPLC method has been developed for Clotrimazole residue analysis, and can be applied for the cleaning control analysis of the lotion and ointment equipment line. A systematic computer assisted method development was applied to find the optimal conditions. All validation analytical performance parameters are well define with in the acceptance criteria as indicated in below validation Table 1.

Conclusion :

On the basis of this study, it appears that the use of UPLC for the quantification of API residues in cleaning validation samples in product formulation area is practical. The time reducing and solvent saving characteristics of UPLC method are very advantageous, compared to

Table 1

Parameter evaluated	Acceptance criteria	Observation
Precision	System precision	RSD of 6 replicates NMT 2.0%
	Method precision	RSD of 6 assay values NMT 2.0%
	Intermediate precision	RSD of 12 assay values NMT 2.0%
Linearity	$r^2 > 0.99$	1.0
Limit of detection (LOD) – 0.1 ppm	RSD should below 33%	0.48%
Limit of quantitation (LOQ) – 0.33 ppm	RSD should below 10%	1.29%
Recovery (%)	Should be more than 85%	Found more than 95% in each case (SS/glass)
Robustness	System suitability should complies at all conditions taken for experiment	Complies
Solution stability	RSD should not be more than 2.0% up to 48 h	0.26%

the most widely used conventional HPLC technique. The enhanced sensitivity of the UPLC-UV method compared to conventional HPLC does not necessitate the use of a mass spectrometry detector, which is expensive and not widespread in cleaning control analysis. The concept of applying a generic method for several API residues for a product line is feasible and practical if the structure and properties of compounds to be determined are similar.

References

- FDA, Guide to Inspections of Validation of Cleaning Processes, 1993.
- Guide to Inspections of Validation of Cleaning Processes, Reference Material for FDA Investigators and Personnel, Food and Drug Administration, Washington, DC, July, 1993, pp. 1-6.
- Cleaning Validation Guidelines – Good Manufacturing Practice, Health Products and Food Branch Inspectorate, Canada, 2004.
- Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient Committee, Guidance on Aspects of Cleaning Validation in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient Plants, 2000.
- T. Mirza, R. C. George, J. R. Bodenmiller and S. A. Belanich, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1998, **16**, 939.
- Z. Katona, L. Vincze, Z. Végh, Á. Trompler and K. Ferenczi-Fodor, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2000, **22**, 349.
- M. B. Boca, E. Pretorius, C. Kgaje and Z. Apostolides, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2008, **46**, 631.
- R. Debono, S. Stefanou, M. Davis and G. Walis, *Pharm. Technol.*, 2002, **26**, 72.
- K. M. Jenkins, A. J. Vanderwielen, J. A. Armstrong, L. M. Leonard, G. P. Murphy and N. A. Piros, *J. Pharm. Sci. Technol.*, 1996, **50**, 6.
- E. L. Simmonds, W. J. Lough and M. R. Gray, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2006, **40**, 631.
- L. Liu and B. W. Pack, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2007, **43**, 1206.
- K. J. Fountain, M. VanWingerden and D. M. Diehl, *LC-GC North-Am.*, 2007, **25**, 66.
- J. Lamòropoulos, G. A. Spanos and N. V. Lazaridis, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2000, **23**, 421.
- M. J. Nozal, J. L. Bernal, L. Toribio, M. T. Martin and F. J. Diez, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002, **30**, 285.
- T. Mirza, M. J. Lunn, F. J. Keeley, R. C. George and J. R. Bodenmiller, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1999, **19**, 747.
- M. B. Boca, Z. Apostolides and E. Pretorius, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2005, **37**, 461.
- T. T. Fazio, A. K. Singh, E. R. M. Keodor Hackmann and M. I. R. M. Santoro, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2007, **43**, 1495.
- R. Klinkenberg, B. Streel and A. Ceccato, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2003, **32**, 345.
- M. E. Swartz and B. Murphy, *Am. Lab.*, 2005, **37**, 22.
- M. E. Swartz, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 2005, **28**, 1253.
- S. Görög, *Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2007, **26**, 12.
- S. Görög, *Anal. Sci.*, 2004, **20**, 767.
- R. J. Forsyth and D. V. Haynes, *Pharm. Technol.*, 1998, **22**, 104.
- D. A. LeBlanc, *Pharm. Technol.*, 1998, **22**, 136.
- G. L. Fourman and M. V. Mullen, *Pharm. Technol.*, 1993, **17**, 54.
- ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline, Q2A, Text on Validation of Analytical Procedures, October 27, 1994.
- ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline, Impurities in New Drug Products.